

A New Synthesis of Quinazolines. Part II.

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In Part I of this investigation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 297) proof has been adduced that when ethyl carbamate condenses with an acylamine ($\text{RCO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{X}$) 4-oxyquinazolines are formed, sometimes in good yield, depending on the nature of R and the substituent X in the aromatic nucleus. The present investigation arose out of the fact that it seemed probable that if R is PhCH_2 , there may be a chance of an *isoquinoline* (I) ring-formation. In view of the fact that so few methods are available for the synthesis of *isoquinoline* derivatives, it seemed of interest to explore this possibility.

The ring may also close in the alternative direction to give a benzyl quinazolinone (II). Since a methyl group or a part of it directs substitution to a greater extent to the *ortho*-position than NH_2 or NH , the probability was an *isoquinoline* would be formed. If the product is an *isoquinoline* derivative it would have very feeble basic property or none at all, whilst if the product is a quinazolinone the substance would show the usual basicity of the series. On actual experiment we find that it is a quinazolinone that is formed and in spite of thorough search we failed to locate any *isoquinoline* derivative in the product. The investigation was continued because the quinazolines have an intrinsic interest of their own; besides the quaternary salts of a few have been found by Gabriel and Colmann (D. R.-P. 161401) to have a lowering effect on the blood pressure.

The conditions of experiment are approximately the same as found by Bhattacharya, Bose and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 279) but the yields are not satisfactory.

Starting substance.	Percentage yield of the quinazoline.		
Phenaceto-anilide	...	...	8.5
Phenaceto- <i>o</i> -toluidide	...	...	3.0
Phenaceto- <i>m</i> -toluidide	...	...	9.0
Phenaceto- <i>p</i> -toluidide	...	...	7.2
Phenaceto- <i>o</i> -anisidide	...	...	13.0
Phenaceto- <i>p</i> -anisidide	...	...	10.2
Phenaceto- <i>o</i> -xylylide	...	...	2.8
Phenaceto- α -naphthalide	...	...	36.7
Phenaceto- β -naphthalide	...	...	31.4

These quinazolines give well-defined monomethyl derivatives when they are treated with methyl iodide and 2.8 % potassium hydroxide solution. These according to Bogert and Seil (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 534) are *N*-methyl derivatives.

In the next paper we will describe some further condensation products derived from the form II.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following phenacetyl derivatives of aromatic amines used in this investigation do not appear to have been described before. The general method of preparation has been to heat phenylacetic acid (1 mol.), the amine (1 mol.) with a few drops of pyridine in an oil-bath at 160°-170°. The cooled product after treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid is usually crystallised from alcohol or from other suitable solvents.

Phenacetyl derivative, $C_6H_5 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO \cdot NHR$.

Quantity of phenylacetic acid.	Quantity of amine.	M.p. of product	Analysis :P. c. of N.	
			Found.	Calc.
14 gm.	10 gm. <i>m</i> -toluidine.	75°. needles	6.32	6.20
13	12 ,, <i>o</i> -anisidine.	84°	5.82	5.80
13	12 ,, <i>p</i> -anisidine.	124°	5.94	5.80
13.6	14.3 ,, α -naphthalide	175°.	5.39	5.36
13.6	14.3 ,, β -naphthalide.	158°.	5.43	5.36
13.6	12.1 ,, <i>o</i> -xylylide.	158°.	5.97	5.85

Condensation of Phenacetanilide with Ethyl Carbamate : Formation of 2-Benzyl-4-oxyquinazoline (Formula I).—Phenacetanilide (7 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.) and phosphoric oxide (20 g.) were thoroughly mixed in a flask and to the mixture 30 c.c. of xylene were introduced. The reaction was completed by heating in an oil-bath at 130°-140° for 3 hours. The xylene solution was freed from the solids and to the cold mixture water containing about 2 c.c. of hydrochloric acid was introduced. The resulting solution was filtered and carefully neutralised. The precipitated solids were collected and crystallised from hot absolute alcohol in beautiful plates; m.p. 247°. The substance is soluble in alcohol, alkali and also in dilute acids. (Found: N, 11.90. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 11.86 per cent.)

2-Benzyl-3-methyl-4-quinazolone.—The preceding substance (0.8 g.) was dissolved in 15 c.c. of 2.8% solution of potassium hydroxide in methyl alcohol and the solution refluxed with methyl iodide (10 c.c.) on the water-bath for 6 hours. The product was then evaporated to dryness, and the residue was washed well with dilute alkali. The substance was crystallised in beautiful, small, colourless needles from dilute alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal. Yield 0.4 gm., m. p. 95°. (Found: N, 11.32. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.20 per cent.)

The *picrate* crystallised out of ethyl alcohol as yellow, silky needles, m. p. 170°.

Condensation of Phenaceto-o-toluidide with Ethyl Carbamate : Formation of 2-Benzyl-8-methyl-4-oxyquinazoline.

Phenaceto-o-toluidide (7.5 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.) and phosphoric oxide (20 g.) were thoroughly mixed in a flask and to the mixture 30 c.c. of xylene were introduced. The mixture was heated on the oil-bath at 140° for 3 hours. The quinazoline was isolated just as in the case of 2-benzyl-4-oxyquinazoline. On crystallisation from absolute alcohol it was obtained in slightly yellowish plates, m. p. 198°. The substance is soluble in alcohol, alkali and also in dilute acids. (Found: N, 11.08. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.2 per cent.)

The *picrate* of the above quinazoline was prepared, by mixing saturated solutions of the quinazoline and picric acid in absolute alcohol. Recrystallisation of the product from dilute alcohol gave beautiful, yellow, silky needles, m. p. 153°.

*Condensation of Phenaceto-m-toluidide with Ethyl Carbamate :
Formation of 2-Benzyl-7-methyl-4-oxyquinazoline.*

A mixture of phenaceto-*m*-toluidide (7.5 g.) ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.) and xylene (35 c. c.) was heated on the oil-bath for 3 hours at 130-140° and the product was isolated as usual. The quinazoline was obtained in colourless plates on crystallisation from absolute alcohol, m. p. 230°. The substance is soluble in alcohol, alkali and also in dilute acids. (Found: N, 11.27. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.20 per cent.)

The *picrate* of the above quinazoline, prepared in the usual manner, was obtained in yellow, silky needles on crystallisation from alcohol; m. p. 168°. (Found: N, 14.81. $C_{22}H_{17}O_8N_5$ requires N, 14.61 per cent.).

*Condensation of Phenaceto-p-toluidide with Ethyl Carbamate :
Formation of 2-Benzyl-6-methyl-4-oxyquinazoline.*

The substance was prepared by heating a mixture of phenaceto-*p*-toluidide (7.5 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.) and xylene (35 c. c.) on the oil-bath at 130-140° for 3 hours. The product was isolated in the usual way. When crystallised from absolute alcohol it was obtained in colourless plates, m. p. 239°. (Found: N, 11.16. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.2 per cent.).

2-Benzyl-3:6-dimethyl-4-quinazoline.—This was prepared exactly in the same way as 2-benzyl-3-methyl-4-quinazoline. The product was recrystallised from dilute alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal when colourless small needles, m. p. 116°, were obtained. (Found: N, 10.74. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 10.60 per cent.).

The *picrate* was obtained in the same way as that of 2-benzyl-6-methyl-4-quinazoline. It had m. p. 194° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 14.53. $C_{22}H_{17}O_8N_5$ requires N, 14.61 per cent.).

*Condensation of Phenaceto-p-anisidide with Ethyl Carbamate :
Formation of 2-Benzyl-6-methoxy-4-oxyquinazoline.*

Phenaceto-*p*-anisidide (8 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.) and xylene (35 c. c.) were well mixed in a flask and heated for 3 hours at 130-140° and the product was isolated as usual. On crystallisation from alcohol the above quinazoline was obtained

in colourless plates, m. p. 241°. (Found: N, 10.62. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.52 per cent.).

2-Benzyl-3-methyl-6-methoxy-4-quinazolone.

One gm of the preceding substance was dissolved in 15 c. c. of 2% solution of caustic potash in methyl alcohol and the solution was refluxed with 1 c. c. of methyl iodide for 6 hours. The product was isolated and crystallised from dilute alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal; colourless needles, m. p. 121°. (Found: N, 10.07. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.00 per cent.).

The *picrate* was obtained in the usual way in yellow, silky needles, m. p. 198°. (Found: N, 14.26. $C_{22}H_{17}O_9N_5$ requires N, 14.14 per cent.).

Condensation of Phenaceto-o-anisidide with Ethyl Carbamate: Formation of 2-Benzyl-8-methoxy-4-oryquinazoline.

The substance was obtained by heating a mixture of phenaceto-*o*-anisidide (8 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.), and xylene (35 c. c.) for 3 hours at 130-140°. The product was isolated as usual. On crystallisation from absolute alcohol it was obtained in colourless plates, m. p. 257°. (Found: N, 10.54. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.52 per cent.).

2-Benzyl-3-methyl-8-methoxy-4-quinazolone was prepared and isolated as usual. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal, colourless needles, m. p. 138°, were obtained. (Found: N, 10.23. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.00 per cent.).

The *picrate* was prepared by the usual method; yellow, silky needles from absolute alcohol, m. p. 191°. (Found: N, 14.35. $C_{22}H_{17}O_9N_5$ requires N, 14.14 per cent.).

Condensation of Phenaceto-o-xylylidide with Ethyl Carbamate: Formation of 2-Benzyl-7:8-dimethyl-4-oxyquinazoline.

Phenaceto-*o*-xylylidide (8 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.) and xylene (35 c. c.) were heated at 130-140° for three hours, and the product obtained as before. On crystallisation from absolute alcohol, colourless plates melting at 189° were obtained. (Found: N, 10.71. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 10.60 per cent.).

The *picrate* of the preceding quinazolone was isolated as before and was obtained in yellow needles from alcohol, m. p. 165°. (Found: N, 14.39. $C_{23}H_{19}O_8N_5$ requires N, 14.2 per cent.).

*Condensation of Phenaceto- α -naphthalide with Ethyl Carbamate:
Formation of 2-Benzyl-7:8-benzo-4-oxyquinazoline.*

A mixture of phenaceto- α -naphthalide (9 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.) and xylene (35 c. c.) was heated for three hours at 130-135°. The quinazoline came down by the addition of ice-cold water to the cold reaction mixture. Colourless crystals of the substance were obtained from pyridine, m. p. 265°. (Found: N, 9.91. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.79 per cent.).

*Condensation of Phenaceto- β -naphthalide with Ethyl Carbamate:
Formation of 2-Benzyl-6:7- or 5:6-benzo-4-oxyquinazoline.*

A mixture of phenaceto- β -naphthalide (9 g.), ethyl carbamate (6 g.), phosphoric oxide (20 g.) and xylene (35 c. c.) was heated for 3 hours at 130-135°. The product was isolated by the addition of water to the cold solid reaction mixture. On crystallisation from pyridine, the substance was obtained in crystalline form, m. p. 278°. (Found: N, 10.02. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.79 per cent.).